

external reaction, but with such extensive internal reaction, with swelling of the arytenoid folds and aryepiglottic tissues, that it was almost necessary to do a tracheotomy.

In the case I cited, the boy had had no treatment for a week, when superficial ulceration appeared all over the skin of the nose and cheek. It was extraordinarily painful. The pain following the use of radium is what patients object to. There is no question of its activity.

DR. DELAVAN, closing the discussion: I cannot conceal my great satisfaction with regard to the cases which Dr. Coakley has presented. I have been studying this matter of nasopharyngeal fibroma ever since I was an undergraduate student. I have seen the best surgeons take these cases and end with very unsatisfactory results. Statistics show that surgical procedures of any kind are dangerous. Evulsion, removal with a snare, and other methods, may be followed by hemorrhage. As far as I can compile statistics on the subject, there are five deaths in a hundred, as the result of shock or hemorrhage. There is always the danger of recurrence. The application of radium requires a certain amount of skill, but no surgical skill.

Sodium Bicarbonate in Hay-fever. K. E. KELLOGG, *N. Y. Med. Jour.*, Aug. 21, 1915.

Kellogg is of the opinion that hay-fever is essentially an acidosis and by reason of certain irritating qualities of the blood the mucous membranes become hypersensitive. His experience covers fifty cases and in ninety per cent. of them sodium bicarbonate given in dram doses three times a day produced a marked amelioration of symptoms, of which seventy per cent. were completely relieved after a few days' treatment. The remaining ten per cent. were also benefitted, although not so markedly as the others.

The improvement of the local symptoms seemed to be independent of the exciting cause (cotton weed, rag weed, wild rose, golden rod). In three cases the internal administration of the sodium bicarbonate was supplemented by a nasal spray with a solution of the same alkali.

Kellogg suggests that the sodium bicarbonate acts by preventing the pollen toxins from going into solution. ED.